

Navigation between stopovers by migratory geese: comparing geomagnetic and geographic loxodromes, great circle routes and real trajectories

Ali Moayedī^{*1}, Jed A. Long^{†2}, Andrea Kölzsch^{‡3,4} and Urška Demšar^{§1}

¹School of Geography & Sustainable Development, University of St Andrews, St Andrews, Scotland, UK

²Department of Geography & Environment, Centre for Animals on the Move, Western University, London, Ontario, Canada

³Ecology Department, Radboud Institute for Biological and Environmental Sciences (RIBES), Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands

⁴Department of Migration, Max Planck Institute of Animal Behaviour, Radolfzell, Germany

GISRUK 2025

Summary

This study analyses the migration of a greater white-fronted goose (*Anser albifrons*), comparing observed flight paths between stopovers with theoretical geomagnetic loxodromes, geographic loxodromes, and great circle routes. Observed trajectories showed limited alignment with the theoretical routes, especially during spring migration, suggesting adaptive responses to environmental influences.

KEYWORDS: avian migration, ecological GIScience, trajectory analysis, geomagnetic loxodrome, geographic loxodrome

1. Introduction

Migratory birds navigate across thousands of kilometres using sophisticated systems that integrate multiple sensory cues (Mouritsen, 2018). The foundational map-and-compass model (Kramer, 1953) explains this as a combination of a map sense for positional awareness and a compass sense for maintaining direction. Key sources of compass orientation include celestial cues, such as the Sun, stars, and polarised skylight, which provide a reference for geographic north (Emlen, 1975), and the geomagnetic field, with its predictable intensity, inclination, and declination, which serves as a reference for geomagnetic north (Lohmann et al., 2022). These cues have inspired theoretical migration routes, including the geographic loxodrome and the geomagnetic loxodrome (**Figure 1**).

The shortest path between two points along the Earth's surface is termed the great circle route, but its practicality for animal navigation is limited by the continuously changing heading it requires relative to geographic north (Alerstam, 2001). The geographic loxodrome (or rhumb line), in contrast, offers a simpler approach by maintaining a constant bearing relative to true north, albeit at the cost of longer travel distances (Åkesson & Hedenström, 2007). Geomagnetic-based strategies, such as the geomagnetic loxodrome, provide an alternative method of navigation by maintaining a steady course relative to the geomagnetic north (Åkesson & Bianco, 2017).

* am636@st-andrews.ac.uk

† jed.long@uwo.ca

‡ akoelzsch@ab.mpg.de

§ urska.demsar@st-andrews.ac.uk

Figure 1 (a) Navigation paths: the great circle route, the geographic loxodrome (constant angle to geographic meridians, grey), and the geomagnetic loxodrome (constant angle to geomagnetic meridians, orange). (b) Angular relationship between geographic and geomagnetic headings.

Despite advancements in understanding theoretical migration routes, most studies focus on entire migratory journeys, often overlooking the critical role of stopovers—key locations where birds rest and refuel. For many species, including geese, stopovers serve as consistent navigational goals, with individuals returning to the same sites annually (Kölzsch et al., 2016). By focusing on segment-based navigation between stopovers, this study uses trajectory measures derived from spatial data to evaluate navigation strategies, demonstrating the potential of GIScience to model, quantify, and compare migratory paths, enhancing our understanding of ecological processes.

2. Data and Methods

This study focused on a single adult greater white-fronted goose (*Anser albifrons*) during the 2018 spring (1 March–31 May) and autumn (15 August–15 November) migration periods. This individual was selected for this pilot project from a dataset containing high-resolution GPS fixes collected over a decade from 117 adult geese tagged in breeding areas on Kolguyev Island (Russia) and at wintering sites in the Netherlands and Germany (Kölzsch et al., 2016). Future analyses will extend to the entire dataset.

Data were pre-processed by discarding fixes with fewer than four satellites or implausibly high speeds. Stationary periods—stopovers, nesting, and moulting sites—were identified based on duration and radius thresholds (Kölzsch et al., 2016) and excluded to isolate active migratory flights. Low-speed data (<1.7 m/s) were filtered out to retain only migratory flights (Zein et al., 2021). Migration was segmented into discrete flights between stopovers, discarding segments <10 km or with low linearity (geodesic to cumulative distance ratio <0.6). To capture the bird's departure orientation, the initial heading was calculated as the average of two bearings: from the final position at the stopover to the first position

after departure and from the first to the second position after departure. This method reflects the bird's initial directional intent upon leaving the stopover.

Three theoretical routes were computed for each retained segment to evaluate the goose's navigational strategies, using the initial heading as the starting directional input. The geographic loxodrome was computed by continuously projecting the bird's position along a fixed bearing relative to geographic north. The geomagnetic loxodrome was calculated as a trajectory with a constant bearing relative to geomagnetic north. The bearing was adjusted iteratively using local, real, contemporaneous and co-located geomagnetic declination values extracted from raster data produced by MagGeo (Benitez-Paez et al., 2021). The iterative process for loxodromes was terminated when further steps increased the distance to the destination. Finally, the great circle route was calculated as the shortest path on the Earth's surface between the segment's start and end points. We then applied dynamic time warping (DTW) (Müller, 2007) with a custom Haversine metric to measure how closely each theoretical route matched the actual coordinates. Because segment lengths vary, DTW values were normalised by the alignment path length. Lower DTW scores indicate a closer match to the observed path.

3. Results

The analysis of the goose's autumn and spring migration revealed segment-specific movement patterns. While most autumn segments exhibited high linearity, indicating direct flights, spring segments 2 and 3 displayed extremely low linearity and minimal geodesic distances, suggesting localised movements (**Table 1**). These segments were excluded from further analyses.

Table 1 Segment characteristics for autumn and spring migration periods

Season	Segment ID	Cumulative distance (km)	Geodesic distance (km)	Linearity (%)
Autumn	1	85	84	98
	2	173	138	80
	3	3197	2289	72
	4	589	560	95
Spring	1	2280	1470	65
	2	357	10	3
	3	412	12	3
	4	1659	1542	93

The results reveal diverse patterns in the alignment of real and theoretical trajectories across segments and seasons (**Table 2**). Here, the “expected heading” refers to the initial bearing required for a theoretical route to guide the bird to its final stopover. In autumn, segment 1 shows strong alignment with theoretical routes, reflected in low DTW values, despite its observed initial heading deviating from expected values. Interestingly, this is the only segment crossing a large water body, where the lack of landmarks may necessitate reliance on compass-based loxodromes. In contrast, segment 3 begins with an initial heading that closely matches the geomagnetic loxodrome's expectation, yet its high DTW highlights subsequent deviations from that route. A more extreme case is observed in spring segment 4, where the bird's actual heading diverges substantially from all theoretical expectations, leading the simulated loxodromes to terminate far from the real endpoint (**Figure 2**).

Table 2 Observed and expected headings for theoretical routes, with normalised DTW scores reflecting route alignment

Season	Segment ID	Initial heading (°)	ML expected heading (°)	GL expected heading (°)	GC expected heading (°)	DTW (observed vs. ML)	DTW (Observed vs. GL)	DTW (observed vs. GC)
Autumn	1	170	164	161	161	5	5	3
	2	187	228	224	225	29	28	18
	3	243	241	232	248	162	350	157
	4	224	251	250	253	107	105	16
Spring	1	54	52	56	48	157	177	192
	4	82	38	45	35	372	347	119

Figure 2 Comparison of observed flight paths with geomagnetic loxodrome, geographic loxodrome, and great circle routes for (a) spring and (b) autumn migrations. Stopover locations are depicted as white circles with red outlines.

4. Conclusion and Future Directions

This study highlights the utility of spatial trajectory analysis in GIScience to model migratory paths and study avian navigation. While geomagnetic and geographic loxodromes provide useful approximations for certain segments, the observed data reveal that the goose does not strictly follow these routes. Environmental factors such as wind direction, resource availability, and topographic barriers likely play critical roles in shaping migration (Åkesson & Hedenström, 2000). Future research will investigate the influence of wind conditions at departure and turning points, as well as the role of topography and landscape barriers. Expanding the analysis to include wind-aligned and magnetoclinic routes could further illuminate geese's navigational strategies.

References

- Åkesson, S., & Bianco, G. (2017). Route simulations, compass mechanisms and long-distance migration flights in birds. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, 203(6), 475–490.
- Åkesson, S., & Hedenström, A. (2000). Wind selectivity of migratory flight departures in birds. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 47(3), 140–144.

- Åkesson, S., & Hedenström, A. (2007). How migrants get there: migratory performance and orientation. *BioScience*, 57(2), 123–133.
- Alerstam, T. (2001). Detours in bird migration. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*, 209(3), 319–331.
- Benitez-Paez, F., Brum-Bastos, V. da S., Beggan, C. D., Long, J. A., & Demšar, U. (2021). Fusion of wildlife tracking and satellite geomagnetic data for the study of animal migration. *Movement Ecology*, 9(1), 31.
- Emlen, S. T. (1975). Migration: orientation and navigation. In *Avian Biology* (pp. 129–219). Elsevier.
- Kölzsch, A., Müskens, G. J. D. M., Kruckenberg, H., Glazov, P., Weinzierl, R., Nolet, B. A., & Wikelski, M. (2016). Towards a new understanding of migration timing: slower spring than autumn migration in geese reflects different decision rules for stopover use and departure. *Oikos*, 125(10), 1496–1507.
- Kramer, G. (1953). Wird die Sonnenhöhe bei der Heimfindeorientierung verwertet? *Journal für Ornithologie*, 94(3), 201–219.
- Lohmann, K. J., Goforth, K. M., Mackiewicz, A. G., Lim, D. S., & Lohmann, C. M. F. (2022). Magnetic maps in animal navigation. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, 208(1), 41–67.
- Mouritsen, H. (2018). Long-distance navigation and magnetoreception in migratory animals. *Nature*, 558(7708), Article 7708.
- Müller, M. (Ed.). (2007). Dynamic Time Warping. In *Information Retrieval for Music and Motion* (pp. 69–84). Springer.
- Zein, B., Long, J. A., Safi, K., Kölzsch, A., Wikelski, M., Kruckenberg, H., & Demšar, U. (2021). Simulation experiment to test strategies of geomagnetic navigation during long-distance bird migration. *Movement Ecology*, 9(1), 46.

Biographies

Ali Moayedi is a PhD candidate at the University of St Andrews. His research focuses on avian navigation and migration, integrating GIScience, movement analysis, and environmental data.

Jed A. Long is an Associate Professor at Western University. His research focuses on GIScience, spatial ecology, and movement analysis, primarily using GPS tracking and space-time modelling to study movement patterns in humans and animals.

Andrea Kölzsch is an Assistant Professor at Radboud University, Nijmegen, and an affiliated researcher at the Max Planck Institute of Animal Behaviour. Her research explores the movement ecology of avian migrants through high-resolution GPS tracking and analytical platforms.

Urška Demšar is a Senior Lecturer in Geoinformatics at the University of St Andrews. Her research interests include spatio-temporal visual analytics and movement analysis, with interdisciplinary applications in ecology and human mobility.